

Gear Chats and AI: The New Way to Buy

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Abstract

This white paper examines the rapidly expanding role of AI-driven and human-powered chat systems in the outdoor gear industry, drawing on the author's direct experience as a gear expert and long-time practitioner in AI and customer support. It analyzes how chatbots are built, how human experts operate behind the scenes, and how customer behavior divides into three distinct tiers that shape sales outcomes. The paper highlights systemic challenges—inventory shortages, inadequate sales training, poor vendor knowledgebases, and misaligned customer-service redirects—while offering nine practical recommendations for vendors and chat companies seeking to improve customer experience and conversion rates. Through real examples and operational insights, the paper argues that effective gear chat requires a blend of human expertise, targeted AI assistance, and a realistic understanding of modern shopper priorities in a difficult economy. The result is a grounded, insider view of how AI and human experts together are reshaping the way outdoor gear is bought online.

Introduction

If you have spent any time shopping for outdoor gear in the last year, you've no doubt noticed the ever-present chatbots in the bottom right corner of vendors' web pages inviting you to ask questions. Shoppers all wonder, exactly what is this? Is it a person, AI, or both? How does this whole thing work? No matter the answer, the chatbot growth rate is expected to be [23 percent per year](#) [1].

The appeal is that either a real person like a river guide or a ski expert guides you on a purchase decision. In some cases, it's not a person, but rather a cleverly designed AI. As it turns out, I'm probably a very good person to help explain this mystery. One of my graduate degrees is in Computer Science, and during my years at IBM, I worked with super AI Watson in cutting-edge pharmaceuticals. Watson famously won Jeopardy in 2011 and became world famous as a leader for natural language processing. I still use AI many times a day as a principle investigator on an astrophysics Dark Matter research project.

I am also a gear expert, and have worked for a chat company as the expert you get to when you do chat.

You may not be aware of just how many of these AI/chatbot systems are out there. They cover a far larger foot print than the outdoor gear industry. They are everywhere now, and as you may already know, Amazon, [UPS Virtual Assistant](#) [2], and many electronics dealers all use them. There are even [websites for people to find jobs](#) [3] as a gear expert and become the person who chats with customers.

Here, we are just looking at the outdoor gear sector. There are many players in this arena too. From the largest [Gearinc](#) [4] with thousands of gear experts, to new up-and-comer [Withremark](#) [5] that has less than 100. [REI](#) [6] and Backcountry [Gearheads](#) [7] are also very popularly used chat services.

To really understand what's behind the veil, I decided to join one of the gear expert companies, and see what life on the other side of the chatbot symbol was like. I had an odd applicant problem, however. I was wildly over qualified, so I wondered if anyone would take me seriously. We've all been rejected for having too much experience at some point. In my case, I am currently a ski patroller who's going to senior level this season and I am a bike patroller on the same hill over the summer. Being on bike patrol resulted in my becoming a fully [Certified Shimano Mechanic](#), [8] a Trek guide (highest level) and an equal investment in Sram, Fox, and several other major manufacturers. Before ski patrol, I was a triathlete, and won my nationals in sprint and international distances between 2005 – 2007 for the 200-pound weight class. My wife and I also compete in open ocean distance swimming races, have an extensive collection of great climbing gear, and I used to guide teams out on their first snowshoe and camping expeditions in the Appalachian mountains.

After a little inquiry, I got an invitation to join one of the chat companies as a gear expert for outdoor brands. Everyone joining the team introduced themselves to the team on the internal meetup group online. Before long, I was in and chatting away and I was trained and assigned to about a dozen client companies. Most of these were names you'd know very well. I quickly realized my gear expert company had two categories of chat support, AI for the budget-conscious, and real human gear experts for the companies with more marketing capital. I will tell you about both.

Life inside the Chat World: Customers

There are basically three types of customers who shop gear vendor websites.

Tier 1 – These are customers who are just randomly browsing, with no real mission, and perhaps just curious onlookers. We've all done it.

Tier 2 – These are shoppers who have a mission, of which the vendor site is only a part. They are looking for a specific product like a tent or skis and check in 4 or 5 sports websites for the lowest price, or for a sale, or perhaps additional product information.

Tier 3 – These shoppers almost always already have something in the cart for potential purchase when they chat. On the gear expert side, we see that right up front. They may be past or repeat customers, and they are the most serious buyers any vendor can get. In the end, they buy more than the other two tiers combined.

Life inside the Chat World: AI

Our chat company’s AI offering was orchestrated by a small group of company programmers who had backgrounds similar to my own. Their job was to fabricate the AI framework for clients based upon a knowledgebase they assembled and likely customer inquiries. The knowledgebase was a hybrid of information garnered from the vendor’s website, and a series of discussions with the client. AI would hopefully unite the right question to the right knowledgebase item. This is accomplished via the classic AI model, which I will reproduce in layman’s terms below.

The challenge for programmers is that **middle red ring**. You see, context is everything. As we all know, [many English words have multiple meanings](#). [9] The word “bat” could be an aluminum slugger, or a small cave-dwelling mammal, or something women do with their eyes. Humans are far better at context than computers, and those older grey-haired people have more experience than younger adults, who are far better than their children. Experience, particularly human experience, is very hard to replace.

Life inside the Chat World: Gear Experts

Once I was on the job, I realized that there were a few things I had to get used to. First was the way I got my work. Everything I needed was on my laptop. I had a single pane of glass application with my knowledgebase, the customer cart view, and the vendor site the customer was working with as a shopper. The shopper's cart was almost always full with the items we were about to discuss. I had a vendor-specific knowledgebase that covered many questions, and a recommendation tool that was up-to-date with stock availability, item color, and size. Nonetheless, work was never steady. This was largely an evening and weekend job, where I could get as many as 12 – 15 chats per hour. The pay was just under \$4 a chat, but I never knew when a chat request would pop up on my screen. Many hours passed with only 3 or 4 chats in 60 minutes. I ended up serving about 200 chats a week on average. After each chat, the customer rated me, which made up my customer service score.

My boss was a terrific guy, a former Olympic team competitor who always treated me well. I appreciated our many meetups on Zoom. He let me know that I was the 3rd highest chatter (by volume) in the company, with a 9.6/10 customer score and a 58 percent sales record on a major sports clothing vendor. He said that this was “incredible.” I realized before long that the nicest part of this job was that it satisfied my inner desire to help others. One customer said, “You are the Jedi master,” after I helped him, which was more rewarding than money. Helping others was a key part of the job.

At the same time, a significant number of people were there to chat with no intention of buying anything. If I had to guess, 15 percent of the chats I served were customer service redirects. These were ordering problems, financing, or other things outside the realm of a gear expert. Another 15 percent were unauthorized retrofits on ebikes, chats that really should go to a mechanic, and “please decode my bike's serial number.” Late one night, I had a customer ask me, “What bike do I have?” and this kind of thing was not as rare as I thought.

Life inside the Chat World: Vendors

My dozen vendors included Ebikes, regular bikes, board shorts, bike clothes, skis and even bike selling sites. They were all enduring an economy that could be better, so raising sales numbers would be a blessing. The attraction of our group was the dual offering of both AI and/or real people to serve chats. But there were problems that plagued the entire process. The largest issue is available inventory. It's hard to sell when the vendor is out of stock on popular sizes and models. At this point, the bike industry is going through hard times, and it's not a secret. I even had out-of-stock templates in the general knowledgebase because of the frequency of that occurrence.

Life inside Chat World: Chat Company Management

It did not take me long to realize that all chats were saved and monitored, and our performance was evaluated by more than just Volume x Customer score x Sales percentage, which we saw in the applications. There were clearly two silos, one between the vendor and the chat team management, and another between the customer/buyers and the gear experts. This actually was what created some of the biggest problems in the system.

Steve Jobs extolled the importance of the [customer experience](#) [10] above nearly everything else. A typical chat company hook for marketing would be to tell a potential client sports vendor that “Our experts help your customers get to the right piece of gear.” This sounds great in a business grad school classroom, but reality is not so simple. In a struggling economy, the customer experience isn’t actually the search for the right piece of gear, but rather the [lowest cost item that will competently complete the mission](#). [11]

It’s up to the gear expert to bridge that confidence gap. I recall one day at nationals in triathlon, when a friend looked at all the pricey bikes on the expert section of the rack and commented, “This is a high tech arms race.” He was right. All the expert bikes at the 2005 triathlon nationals were over \$5000, ultra light, and high tech. It’s more like \$10,000 today. So the right piece of gear would likely be the most expensive, lightest bike the buyer could afford. But as I said, a poor economy and COVID shortages have changed the rules. Now athletes consider used bikes, and direct-to-consumer models that significantly lower cost. The customer experience today is the competent gear and right price, not just right gear alone.

How to Pick a Chat Company to Represent an Outdoor Brand

You can’t go through an experience like mine without seeing both the good and the bad together. There are a series of things I believe a wise sports gear vendor should evaluate before signing with any gear Expert/Chat group. These groups fall into 2 camps. It is wise to pick the “a” group.

- a. Those who truly understand and pursue a better customer experience.
- b. All the rest, who are devoted to vendor-focused agreements or company tradition.

1. Look for Better than 30 Percent Sales

The biggest question before paying someone else to help sell gear is what sales are without an expert. Like many things, this has a lot to do with how you measure. For chat calls, the only customer group that really matters is the tier 3 group, namely, the most serious customers. The lower tier 1 and tier 2 shoppers don’t have anything in their carts by definition. Although we don’t have great stats on before and after chat companies enter the scene, we do have great stats

on cart abandonment. [Hotjar](#) [12] did a survey of national cart abandonment stats over several years. The number today is about 70 percent. Meaning, 30 percent actually do follow through and purchase their cart content without chatbot assistance. So, your company's post-chat group profits would start at 31 percent and up. 30 percent and below is what you get from the tier 3 shoppers unaided. My own sales score was 58 percent on a major sports clothing vendor, or roughly double the standard rate unassisted by gear experts. My boss praised me for that, but at the time, neither of us realized that the first 30 percent was free. Of course, all this assumes in-stock merchandise, because no one can sell stuff that's not there. Some inventory woes began with the bike industry [being hit hard](#) [13] during the pandemic.

2. Look for Sales Training

I neglected to add in my own bio at the top that I had extensive sales and marketing experience and training. I have never come in lower than second place on any large-scale sales contest, even if I was a new employee. It was obvious that our group had some gear training, but no sales training whatsoever. I sent my boss a sales training outline I had just done for a cloud-based IT firm, which he received with his usual graciousness. [Sales training is even more important when times are hard.](#) [14] So, as a vendor of sports gear, you need to ask the team seeking to sell you a chat service, "Show me your sales training modules." If there are none, there will be problems. I can paraphrase a real example of the lack of sales training that I witnessed firsthand.

Customer: I used the company gear search on clearance for all XL shorts, and when I selected the pair I wanted, no XL size was in stock.

Gear Expert: Sorry for this, after testing it, I agree that it is not working correctly. If you like, I will report it to CS in the morning.

Customer: I appreciate that, since we agree on the problem.

After this, the chat closed. But this chat was an obvious sales failure. Had I been the gear expert, I would have realized that customer did not go to the website to do repair work to the vendor's search engine. The customer wanted shorts, and the gear expert never bothered to recommend any other option, even though there were many. This was an inexcusable sales failure. Looking deeper into this chat, I found that the gear expert's company not only has no sales training, but also advertises a 30 percent successful sales figure as a trophy. That's the same 30 percent clients would get from tier 3 shoppers without even hiring a gear expert.

3. Look at the Number of Customer Service Redirects: Fewer is Better

I always felt it was my job to field any request that came to me. But in the lines above my incoming chat stream, I could see past chat history on each customer, many of which had previous gear expert customer service (CS) redirects. Almost every CS redirect is a lost sale. Worse yet, it sends the work we were hired to do back to the people paying us to do it. It would be wise to inquire as to what percentage of CS redirects a chat company has on similar vendors before you sign with them.

In addition, CS redirects cannot just be an email to the vendor. I had many chats saying that vendors had not responded to emails sent days ago. So, I created my own templates with the email, phone number, hours of operation and time zone, plus a picture of the storefront. I made one for every vendor I served, and it really boosted my own customer service score. Vendors who hide from their customers are not good long-term clients.

4. Gear Experts Should Use Targeted AI (copilot) to Help Answer Chats

When fielding questions that don't appear in the pre-canned knowledgebase, or the customer website, it is still possible to answer complex customer questions by looking over outside gear reviews. "How much does the battery of this ebike weigh?" To get this content fast enough to be relevant, you need a smarter, faster Google. After testing numerous AI engines, I found nothing that worked better [than copilot AI](#) [15] set in normal mode. Creative did not provide sufficiently specific answers, concise mode took way too long. Copilot can answer very [involved queries](#), [16] and I used it extensively to great effect. My customer service score always went up when customers saw information from me that was utterly unavailable elsewhere. The very best answers came from an AI result that was moderated or filtered by expert human-powered contextualization. I could very quickly solve unimaginably complex bike and gear questions by combining 65 years of experience with a powerful AI tool pointed at the correct target. There were times when other gear experts within my group sent me questions, knowing I could ferret out the answer.

5. Avoid Prospect and Purge with a Realistic 30-day Testing Period.

I was trained for 13 vendors. Eleven of them were legacy accounts and two were brand new. Serving the old and new differed wildly. The first 30 days in a new account is an undeclared website testing period accomplished by prospecting. As Steve Jobs observed [in this video link](#), [17] customer experience is everything. However, even some of the biggest companies failed to stress test their website to see what percentage of customer inquiry was actually met by the content they posted. I had spent a large portion of my life in the IT world stress testing customer

websites for all sorts of qualities using Mercury Load Runner and Rational Robot. We testers had a saying. “Virtue isn’t virtue till it’s tested.” The knowledgebase I used to answer chats was constructed from a combination of information found on the customer website and details from the vendor working with the chat company management. But when it came to the customer’s chat questions, many of them could not be predicted. As an advanced team setting up the knowledgebase, you just don’t know what you don’t know.

Trust me when I say that customers will ask you impossible things like, “What is the difference between these two nearly identical pieces of gear?” Or, “Out of all your board shorts, which has the shortest inseam?” At the time I started one new account, we had nothing about any of the board shorts on the knowledgebase, just pro deals and other CS related info. The only way to answer these sorts of questions was to scan every item in the store, redirect to CS (a failure) or use Copilot AI. I had to set this up myself because no native vendor web search can answer those sorts of questions. As the first month proceeded, I stepped on more and more land mines due to customer questions not clearly answered on the vendor web site, in our knowledgebase, or even in outside gear testing. I simply could not just re-direct everything to CS, which is a gear expert failure, and almost always is a lost sale.

Customers asked: “Do these shorts have a Velcro fly?” This is not answered anywhere on the website or knowledgebase. That’s when I noticed an interesting phenomenon: after I hit each customer chat landmine; our group knowledgebase grew by one more item that contained the answer I needed yesterday. Someone was prospecting my chats for web stress testing data to benefit the team as a whole. I went back and audited my previous new vendor, and realized the same thing had happened there weeks ago. After hitting 6 or 8 questions no one could answer quickly, I was taken off that vendor. There was the purge. Note to the customer, “The new guys will do far better than he did. “ I have to agree, with a now-fully-populated knowledgebase, created by my struggles, they surely would.

But there is a far better way:

Veteran chat companies use different methods to stress test new clients before going fully live. Microsoft has a beta test period, but the simplest fix is to start doing real gear expert performance metrics between 30 and 60 days instead of from 1 to 30 days. This is far more prudent, and allows chat companies to help vendors refine their own web interface and the knowledgebase to align with customer needs. Tragically, the secret to success where prospect and purge rules is for gear experts to just wait a couple months to add new vendors. Don’t be the first gear expert to step up to new work. This may add to your boss’s stress, but will protect your company statistics beautifully. Or just change the vendor contracts to establish new, more logical startup procedures.

6. Gear Experts Should Lean Towards More Detailed Answers in Chats

Perhaps it's just my opinion, which is based upon [Game Theory](#), [18] but chat customers all engage in a chat because they want more information, not less. In fact, even after thousands of chats, I have never had any customer suggest that I gave them too much info.

So, how long should chat responses be? Should you just give them the short and sweet pre-canned knowledgebase answer or truly pursue researching their questions wherever they lead? Pre-canned robotic answers from humans would be nothing better than turning your human gear experts into a bunch of bots. For tier 3 shoppers, the real answer is in shopper research statistics. [Consumer Gravity](#) [19] did that very study and showed that customers spend 79 days researching high ticket purchases. This is 2.5 months. I knew from my own CS scores that longer, more detailed answers were quickly rewarded with higher customer satisfaction scores. But to test the theory, I ran a trial of about 50 chats. I asked shoppers, "Long answer OK?" before providing the detailed answer. All but one said yes. So, I have to conclude that for tier 3 shoppers (the ones who actually chat) more is better.

7. Gear Experts Should Make Great Use of Sales, Clearances, and Open Box Deals to Ensure Customer Satisfaction

[Hotjar](#) [20] offers nearly 20 reasons for cart abandonment. Number one, at 48 percent, is price. As we observed previously, customers might have sought the "right" piece of gear in a great economy. Today however, in our tougher economic environment, they prefer [the lowest priced item](#) [21] that will competently complete the task. Anytime I helped a customer complete this objective I got a positive review post chat. If the chat company's contract is written in a way that does not acknowledge this reality, then it needs to change. Customers will vote with their feet. Although sports companies would rather sell the \$180 bike shorts that are not on sale, customers flock to the \$30 pair that is on clearance down from \$130. Gear experts cannot change what is in the shopper's wallet.

8. Wise Use of AI: Full Carts Should Always Trigger Real Human Gear Experts over AI

Although AI has a place in gear sales, it is very limited for tier 3 customers. As a rule, AI can be used for tier 1 and 2 shoppers, but the minute someone puts anything in their cart, they should immediately be promoted to tier 3 status and directed to human gear experts. Sales are lost when AI is rejected by purchaser protests. If a buyer has to fight through and be miserable with an AI in order to get to a human gear expert, there is a tendency to just give up or to carry that

frustration over to the gear expert. Customers should never have to say “Operator” or “I want to talk to a human.” I will paraphrase a real example from a chat I took for a ski company.

Customer: “I am trying to get this \$700 ski sale coupon to work, but it doesn’t. Can you help?”

AI: “I don’t see your coupon in our active list, but I do see the 185 cm all mountain ski in our inventory, currently \$1200. It’s in stock and in your size.”

Customer: “Human please! I am not just looking for a ski, I am looking for a sale.”

-At this point I inherited the chat from the AI.

Me: “Sorry about this mix up. Your coupon was for last year, and the AI could not see that people calling in for skis in June want discounted and sale items, not skis to use this weekend. Here is the clearance ski list. Hope that helps.”

This was an AI context failure that could have easily have been prevented by the ‘full cart gets tier 3 treatment’ rules described above.

9. Human Experience Rules & More Experience is Always Better

Human experience, especially of domain experts in skiing, running, biking and other outdoor endeavors can greatly benefit buyers at purchase time. But implementation is everything. Chat teams of gear experts need experienced leadership, sales training, and a real connection with the customer experience. Not only a little training on a new gear line, but also they must understand the vendor’s price and mission.

Don’t hesitate to ask questions about the gear experts serving your account. The simplest metric is (customer service score) x (sales percentage) x (volume). I always kept my total in the top 10 percent of the company, and that took real commitment to the job and detailed study of the vendor websites.

Gear Expert Companies Must Have Their Own Client Vetting Process

The problem with some gear companies is a failure to properly vet new clients. Gear expert companies should have a vetting process that can detail with clear criteria:

- a. Does this vendor have enough time in the business and outside gear testing to answer client requests that are not on their website?
- b. Does the gear expert group have experts specific to this new vendor’s area of sales?

- c. Can a sufficiently robust knowledgebase be developed using the published resources to field 80 percent of customer inquiries?
- d. Is there an option to say, “Can I get back to you on this process?” for the impossible requests?

In the End, the Gear Expert Experience Was Just Plain Fun & Other Key Takeaways

I have to say that my employment experience as a gear expert was fantastic overall. I loved my wonderful boss, and my customers. I loved helping people, no matter the challenge. My wife even loved what I was doing. I had the greatest devotion to my vendors, even making 62 of my own custom knowledgebase templates. But to be fair, taking chats all day and night was exhausting. Many times I took chats at 2, 3 and 4 am from customers all over the world. After 3 months of this, I was walking around in an exhausted haze. I recall one day while on a well-announced vacation, I was biking on the C&O canal with my very patient wife. We were miles from nowhere. While in the woods, I turned on my phone, which barely had a signal, and saw 10 chats unclaimed by other team members. Some had been waiting for 15 minutes. There was no way I was going to let these people go unaided, so I sat at a picnic table in the woods and answered them all. I biked home that night feeling good about what I did, but it wasn't the first time, or nearly the last.

- If you are a vendor, consider my 9 points above as you interview the chat companies who seek your business.
- If you are a chat company, consider your business model and how to better adapt it to the customer experience.
- If you are a customer, you now far better understand what happens when you engage a gear expert in a chat.

AI and gear chats are rapidly changing the way we buy outdoor equipment.

Welcome to the new world. Mahalo!

David Flynn

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